
INCREASING LEARNING OUTCOMES RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS ACTIVITIES THROUGH ACTIVE LEARNING APPROACHES

Abdullah ^{*1}, Moch. Asmawi ¹, Samsudin ¹

^{*1} Department, Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:

The application of the rhythmic gymnastics learning approach must be in accordance with the characteristics of students, for that it requires an innovative and active learning approach according to all the existing characters. The method used is action research using Kemmis and Mc. Taggart with the design of planning, observation, action and reflection. The results showed an increase in rhythmic gymnastics learning outcomes. This is evidenced by the average in the pre cycle which is 43.2 with a percentage of 42.29%, in the first cycle increased to 63.9 with a percentage of 55.26% and in the second cycle increased to 87.3 with a percentage of 100%. So, it can be concluded that the active learning approach can improve the learning outcomes of rhythmic gymnastics. Because the application of an active learning approach is adapted to the characteristics of students who want to learn and facilitate the learning process in understanding the rhythmic gymnastics methods.

Keywords: Learning Outcomes; Rhythmic Gymnastics; Active Learning Approaches.

Cite This Article: Abdullah, Moch. Asmawi, and Samsudin. (2019). "INCREASING LEARNING OUTCOMES RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS ACTIVITIES THROUGH ACTIVE LEARNING APPROACHES." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 6(10), 65-70. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3542259.

1. Introduction

The function of national education is to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of intellectual life of the nation. The curriculum is an element of educational resources that makes a significant contribution to realizing the process of developing the quality of potential learners. The curriculum as an instrument to direct students to become qualified human beings who are capable and proactive in responding to the challenges of the changing times, educated people who believe in and fear God Almighty, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and citizens who are democratic, responsible. To carry out this function the government implements a national education system as stated in Act Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System[1].

One element that supports the achievement of educational goals is good competence from educators or teachers. Teachers play a strategic role in efforts to achieve national education goals, tasks and responsibilities assumed by teachers as educators is very heavy[2]. These duties and responsibilities are to improve the dignity and status of the nation through improving the quality of learning. This hard task is what makes teachers committed to always improve their competence

both pedagogical competence, professional competence, social competence and personal competence[3].

The scope of subject matter of physical and sports physical education learning (PJOK) includes aspects: the scope of games and sports activities, the scope of fitness activities, the scope of gymnastic activities, the scope of rhythmic activities, the scope of water activities, the scope of activities outside the classroom, and the scope of health. Mastery of all scope of PJOK learning is absolutely must have, also with the ability aspects of rhythmic activity. The material contained in rhythmic activities include: free motion, Indonesian Morning Gymnastics (SPI), Physical Fitness Gymnastics (SKJ), and aerobics and other activities. SPI, SKJ and other activities that contain traditional gymnastics are part of rhythmic motion activities whose material and manufacturing process are based on aerobic gymnastics concepts, so aerobic gymnastic material is the main or dominant part in learning rhythmic motion activities.

The SKJ and SPI materials are packaged gymnastics in the order in which they have been done or memorized package exercises. In studying packet gymnastics, what needs to be done is how to memorize the sequence of movements that exist on the package gymnastics using standard accompaniment music. Today many gymnastics packages are circulating in the community and are practiced in schools such as in the 80s there are SPI or Indonesian morning gymnastics. In 1992 there were SKJ package exercises[4]. This SKJ gymnastics is created every four years so that we know SKJ 92, SKJ 96, SKJ 2000, SKJ 2004, SKJ 2008, SKJ 2012. Also gymnastic packages develop with labels; Student Gymnastics, Santri Gymnastics, Scout Gymnastics, Daily Activity Gymnastics, Elementary Gymnastics, Healthy Heart Gymnastics, Worker Gymnastics, Cheerful Healthy Gymnastics, etc. Of all the existing gymnastic packages, if they must be memorized, this will greatly burden PJOK teachers(Antualpa & Paes, 2009).

Existing package exercises are actually created using basic motion material available in aerobic exercise, based on the principles of moving to aerobic exercise. If we already understand and are able to practice or move using the basics of aerobic exercise, and carry out aerobic exercise learning, then we no longer need to bother memorizing the many package exercises as learning material for PJOK rhythm activities[6].

Rhythm activity using aerobics is a relatively new type of activity but in its development this activity is quite popular among the people. The ability of a PJOK teacher to be able to meet the demands of the curriculum must be balanced with efforts to continue learning, renewing knowledge and skills related to his assignments, both as a PJOK teacher and as a member of the community.

In the higher education curriculum actually has included rhythmic gymnastics or aerobics gymnastics material. as part of the motion course. It turns out that graduates from tertiary education have not fully been able to guarantee being able to teach aerobics[7]. Especially in the case of PJOK teachers who have never received aerobics classes. The possibilities below could be the reason why PJOK teachers are less able in mastering aerobic exercise, some of which are: the number of meetings or semester credits that are indeed lacking, when studying college only study or memorize the existing gymnastic packages, or even did not learn the basic concepts of basic aerobic exercise as demanded by the PJOK curriculum. The reason is quite strong that the rhythmic

gymnastic activity using aerobic gymnastic material is a type of activity that is relatively new to our society, when compared to other activities[8]. When a student joins a soccer class or other popular activities, at least before getting the course he knows and practices this game. In contrast to aerobics, students are generally at a minimum ability to recognize and master the basic movements of the rhythmic gymnastics, meaning that they have to make extra hard efforts to be able to master as a provision for PJOK teachers who are required to teach rhythmic gymnastics at school.

During interacting with PJOK teachers on education and training held by the Center for Development and Empowerment of Educators and Education Personnel of Physical Education and Guidance Counseling (PPPPTK PENJAS and BK) information obtained from the field shows that PJOK teachers are not able to do aerobic exercise learning at school. Information obtained after conducting discussions with them, both during the discussion in the process of education and training and personal conversation, why PJOK teachers have not been able to carry out learning rhythmic exercise in general, namely; unavailability of infrastructure that supports the implementation of the learning process of rhythmic gymnastics activities such as; do not have accompaniment music in the form of cassettes or music CDs, tape players, sound systems, videos, and written sources about the rhythmic gymnastics itself[9]. After going through a more open process of discussion, why there are still many PJOK teachers who have not yet learned aerobic exercise because the PJOK teacher's ability to apply learning approaches is still low on aerobic gymnastics material. In this case it will ultimately affect the ability of PJOK teachers in managing learning[10].

The obligation of a teacher is to manage learning. Learning management includes activities; plan, implement, assess learning, and conduct follow-up learning. Teachers are required to manage learning in all spheres of physical education available, including in managing rhythmic gymnastics learning. By looking at the ability to manage weak rhythmic gymnastics learning in Mampang Elementary School 2, Pancoran Mas, Depok City, the authors are very interested in conducting action research on the activities of rhythmic gymnastics using basic aerobic exercise.

2. Materials and Methods

This research applies the action research method (Action Research). By using a research design model Kemmis and Mc.Taggart, in the form of a cycle that includes stages: 1) Planning (planning), 2) action (action), 3) observation (observing) and 4) reflection (reflecting). This research was conducted at Mampang State Elementary School 2, Pancoran Mas, Depok City with the subject of the fifth grade students at the school. Data collection used in this study is the researcher as the main instrument, the format of observation, interviews, observations, field notes and documentation in the form of images, as well as the results of the learning rhythm test which is then validated in consultation with experts (expert judgment) and presented in the form of data qualitative and descriptive statistics to describe the magnitude of the increase that occurred. The application of learning in the approach to students is done with an active learning approach. This learning is carried out on the basic rhythmic gymnastics gymnastic exercises based on active learning approaches, the use of principles, learning approaches that refer to the physical and psychological growth and development of students so as to enable the achievement of learning objectives effectively, efficiently, and fun.

3. Results and Discussions

Based on the data obtained can be seen an increase in the average value obtained by students starting from the initial test from the evaluator of the students' initial data test results with the number of subjects 38 students. Preliminary data obtained from the seven elements of rhythmic gymnastic activity evaluation in the form of variations and combinations of basic motion aerobics marching gymnastics, jumping jacks, double steps, knee ups, v-steps, smoothness, memorization of motion have below the KKM (KKM value = 75). The average value of the initial test results obtained before applying the active learning approach is 42.29% or with a value of 43.2.

The results of the first cycle test that has been done from the assessment of the existing rhythmic gymnastics activity obtained only 31.58% which is complete while the unfinished namely 68.42% of students. According to the data obtained in cycle 1, it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of rhythmic exercise activities in the form of variations and combinations of basic movements of aerobic exercise have changed but have not yet reached the completeness target. This is because most of the students are new to learning the activities of rhythmic gymnastics activities in the form of variations and combinations of basic movements of aerobic exercise. The level of mastery that gets satisfactory results is in the basic motion marching, and memorization of motion with the average of the two elements of evaluation above the KKM. The other five assessment elements are relatively new assessment elements known to students so as to get a value below the KKM limit.

Cycle 2 test there are no students who get a value of 0 to 74, or 100% of students get a value of 75 or above 75. According to the data obtained in cycle 2 it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of rhythmic exercise activities in the form of variations and combinations of basic movements of aerobic exercise have achieved, that is, 100% of students have reached the KKM limit, although there are still relatively many students who score on certain elements of assessment to get the same value as the KKM. The table below illustrates the improvement in learning outcomes from cycle 1 to cycle 2.

Table 1: comparison of cycle 1 results, cycle 2 with graduation

No	Category	KKM	Cyle 1		Cyle 2	
			F	%	F	%
1	Pass	≥ 75	21	55,26%	38	100
2	Not pass	≤ 74	17	44,74%	0	0%
3	Σ		38	100%	38	100%

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that in cycle 1 students passed 21 people (55.26%) students and those who did not pass 17 people (44.74%) students. Whereas in cycle 2 a significant increase was seen in 38 students graduating (100%). Thus, there is an increase in the learning outcomes of rhythmic exercise activities in the form of variations and combinations of basic aerobic exercise seen from cycle 1 compared to cycle 2 more clearly can be seen from the histogram diagram below.

Graph 1: Bar chart of rhythmic gymnastics learning outcomes

Based on cycle 1 reflection some factors that should be of particular concern for implementation in the next cycle are to better control excessive excitement so that students focus more on learning objectives, the use of multimedia approaches if possible needs to be tried, information about learning resources also needs to get the attention of the teacher, also support from various types of learning media. Unstructured independent assignment activities need to be given to students to support the acceleration of the achievement of learning objectives of rhythmic gymnastics activity material in the form of variations and combinations of basic movements of aerobic exercise.

In contrast to the results of the observation of cycle 2, several factors that have been carried out are the provision of independent assignments, and the use of singing media in the implementation of rhythmic gymnastics learning. With the increasing ability in the concept of rhythmic gymnastics activities in the form of variations and combinations of basic aerobic exercise and the use of singing media in learning, this adds to the enthusiasm and activeness of participants in learning rhythmic gymnastics. So, with the achievement of the results above, the action research on the second semester V grade students, Mampang 2 Elementary School, Pancoran Mas, Depok City is sufficient to be carried out with two cycles.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Through an active learning approach, it can improve the learning outcomes of rhythmic gymnastics at SD Negeri Mampang 2, Pancoran Mas, Depok City. The application of the learning approach provides a tiered learning process with adjustments to students to learn a lesson well, in addition it can stimulate students because the active learning approach is more varied and not boring, because elementary school students have the characteristics of analyzing logic concretely.

Based on the results of the research concluded above and in an effort to improve the learning outcomes of PJOK special rhythmic gymnastics materials and other PJOK activity material, several suggestions were made as follows: (1) Physical and health physical education teachers must have awareness in managing learning from planning, implementing and evaluating learning.

(2) Physical and sports physical education teachers must be able to carry out learning in a pleasant atmosphere. (3) Physical and health physical education teachers must be able to foster student activeness in carrying out learning. (4) Physical and health physical education teachers must be able to instill the principles of skills to be learned in learning. (5) Physical and health physical education teachers must be able to apply the use of varied learning media. (6) Physical and health physical education teachers must be able to carry out learning in accordance with the characteristics of students. (7) Physical and health physical education teachers can apply active learning approaches.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: abe007md@ gmail.com